

“TINEA CAPITIS: CURRENT TREATMENT MODALITIES AND ADVANCE THERAPIES”

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INTRODUCTION

Tinea capitis is infection of the hair and skin of the scalp and it is also known as Ringworm or Herpes Tonsurans. The eyebrows as well as eyelashes get affected if the infection is not treated soon. In this type of infection. The fungi can invade the hair shaft; this invasion leads to weaken the hair structure and cause breakage and potential hair loss. It can also infect the outer part of hair follicle.

The main causative organisms of Tinea capitis are

1) MICROSPORUM 2) TRICHOPHYTON

The primarily affecting age of Tinea capitis is about 3-14 years old children but it can affect person of any age. The keratin and

Keratinized tissue of hair gets affected and cause tinea capitis and they affected by dermatophytes.

The two major types of Tinea Capitis are

1. Inflammatory type. 2. Non-inflammatory type

1. Inflammatory type- This is the severe type of disease with a major immune response. This is cause by organism from animal i.e. zoophilic fungi.

Its clinical feature includes- Painful and swollen lesions, Pus filled nodule formation. It also leads to permanent hair loss

2. Non-inflammatory type- It is mild form of disease which is not very serious with a minimal immune response. It is caused by Microsporum audouinni.

Its clinical feature includes- Patchy hair loss, minimal inflammation, gray patch, black dot, mild itching, and no pustules.

ETIOLOGY AND TYPES

Tinea capitis is infection of hair and skin of the scalp. It is caused by two major organisms i.e. Trichophyton species and Microsporum species. The etiology involves Dermatophyte fungi.

The common causative organisms are as follows

1) Trichophyton species - a. Trichophyton tonsurans

b. Trichophyton violaceum

c. Trichophyton schoenleinii

2) Microsporum species - a. Microsporum canis (from cats and dogs)

b. Microsporum audouinii The transmission occurs by –

1) From human-to-human- Which can term as Anthropophilic species transmission.

2) From animal-to-human- Which can term as Zoophilic species transmission.

3) From soil-to-human- Which can term as Geophilic species transmission.

The biological factor causing tinea capitis are: Poor hygiene, weak immune system, young age (i.e. 3-14 years) and directly came in contact with infected animal.

The geographical causes of tinea capitis are the factors found in different regions such as Climate condition, fungal species in regions, High humid regions, Population overcrowding, etc. The regions where Tinea capitis are most common found is North and middle east Africa, Asia, Latin America, etc.

The tinea capitis is the infection of hair and skin of the scalp. It is caused by dermatophytes. The pathophysiology of tinea capitis involves

1) Dermatophyte enter into body: The main causative organisms are Trichophyton and Microsporum. The organism enters into body when comes in direct contact with any infected person or animal. Then the organism affects the outer layer of the scalp which can called as the Stratum corneum of scalp. It starts to hair damaged.

2) Growth and Invasion: The fungi go inside the hair shaft and infect the hair follicles. The microorganisms affect the tissue of hairs known as Keratin ani Keratinized tissue. The

patterns of microorganism affecting hair shaft are of two types:

- A) Endothrix infection: The microorganism's penetration occurs inside the hair shaft and then grows inside scalp. In this type the fungus affects the hair fiber growth but the hair cuticle remains unaffected. Ex. *Trichophyton tonsurans*.
- B) Ectothrix: The fungi grow on the surface of the scalp. In this type the cuticle gets affected. Ex. *Microsporum canis*.
- C) Biological response of body: The body shows two types of responses to the fungus i.e. inflammatory response and non-inflammatory response. Inflammatory response is painful and can lead to permanent hair loss while non-inflammatory response is painless and shows patchy hair loss with mild itching.

These are the steps showing how fungi affect the body's mechanism.

Clinical symptoms of Tinea Capitis

- 1) **Alopecia** - The loss of hair from areas of head. It can be permanent if not treated well. The hair loss starts with one small circular bald patch and then it grows into more than one patch.

The alopecia is of 2 types

- A. Scarring (irreversible) - It is seen in inflammatory variants, especially Kerion. It is painful and has pus inside it.
- B. Non scarring (reversible) - It is seen in Non inflammatory variants. Its lesions appear as gray patch.

- 2) **Black Dot pattern**- It is appeared as patches of hair loss with black dots on scalp. The black dots occur due to remaining part of broken hairs which cause due to fungi growing inside the hair shaft. In this type mild itching can occur.

- 3) **Favus**- The lesions occur as yellowish, cup-shaped crusts around the hairs. It is chronic type and can lasts for years. And it is caused by *Trichophyton schoenlenii*. It can happen due to poor hygiene of hairs.

- 4) **Pruritus**- It causes intense itching into the hair scalp. It can be identified as red, scaly patches with hair loss. It can cause dry scalp, hair thinning and damaged hair shaft.

- 5) **Cervical or Occipital Lymphadenopathy**- It is seen in inflammatory variants. The lymph nodes cause enlargement of patches when scalp infection is present. The signs can

be seen as scalp scaling, pustules, etc.

6) Eyelash or Eyebrow Involvement (in some cases) - It occurs especially in children and immunocompromised patients. It is termed as Tinea faciei or facial dermatophytosis. It is less common. The symptoms are inflamed or patchy hair loss on eyebrow and scaling or loss of eyelashes. The tinea capitis affects the health and the population in following ways.

1) Age distribution - The disease is most commonly seen in the young age children. The children with age 3-14 years is prone to this disease because of immature immune system. It can also be seen in any of age group but the chances of having infection in younger ones are more than adults.

2) Geographic distribution - The tinea capitis disease is cause more into the region which have humid environment. This disease can be seen in any region of the world. But this disease is common in humid area, overcrowded country, country with limited healthcare access and countries with poor hygiene. The regions of Africa, Asia, America shows higher range of this disease.

3) Transmission factors - The mode of transmission can be direct or indirect. The disease can cause if the person comes in direct contact with infected animal. In indirect, the transmission via comb or hat can be prone to the disease, also transmission can occur via sharing personal things.

4) Seasonal variations- The environment is warm and humid in some seasons which can lead to the fungal growth into the environment. In this season the chances of growth and transmission are higher than the other time.

5) Impact on public health- Due to the visible bald scalp between the hairs can leads to the stress and it can cause the increase in absenteeism of school students. It can cause physical as well as mental stress to the patient because of hair loss.

Current Treatment of Tinea Capitis

The tinea capitis is the infection of hair and skin of the scalp caused by dermatophytes. The tinea capitis is treated by combination of oral antifungal medications with topical treatments. The main effective treatment is oral antifungals but topical applications reduce the spreading of infection.

The two types of treatment are,

1. Oral antifungal medications - The oral medications are used to treat infection from inside the body. By this treatment the fungus gets clear from the hair shaft.

GRISEOFULVIN- Used primarily to treat infection of hair, skin and scalp. This drug is Fungistatic i.e. inhibit the growth of fungus. Terbinafine and itraconazole are the alternatives for this drug. The treatment usually taken for 6–8 weeks.

ii) KETOCONAZOLE- It causes inhibition of growth of component of fungal cell membrane and kills fungal. It is used only when other medications are unavailable because it causes severe liver damaged. It is safe for topical application than that of oral.

Iii) Terbinafine- It affects the growth of cell membrane of fungus by inhibiting enzyme. It acts as fungicidal. The treatment is taken for 4–6 weeks. It is effective against Trichophyton species.

IV) Azoles-They are not first-line therapy but they are used when first line drugs are contraindicated (e.g., itraconazole, fluconazole)

2. Topical antifungal-The topical treatments are used to reduce the infection. This does not kill the fungus, but it helps to reduce the spreading of infection.

Topical treatments include following

A) Antifungal shampoo- Antifungal shampoos are used to prevent spreading of scalp infection. It has to be leave for 5- 10 mins on scalp and then wash. It should not contain more chemical agents or APIs to maintain safety. They are used to reduce transmission. The API use in shampoo's are as follows:

KETOCONAZOLE- Used as 1% or 2% in concentration. It reduces the ergosterol synthesis of cell membrane of fungus.

SELENIUM SULFIDE: The concentration to be used is 1% or 2.5%. It is antifungal agent used for 2-3 times in a week and it prevents spreading of infection.

B) Topical creams- The creams are use especially for the ringworms. They are applied to the surrounding of the patches.

IMIDAZOLE (e.g., clotrimazole) - They works on the dermatophytes and damage fungal cell membrane, usually they are fungistatic but sometimes fungicidal.

MICONAZOLE- It should use for 2-4 weeks and apply to scalp daily for 1-2 times to reduce transmission of infection.

3) Natural remedies- It is not the first line treatment but it is used to treat the tinea capitis along with medications. It helps to get relief from infection. The healthcare professional does not suggest to use this but as per our ancient culture of medicines we can use this as it does not cause major side effects. The following remedies can use for fungal infection:

Tea Tree Oil-The diluted tea tree oil with coconut oil can be used directly on the scalp. This oil has antifungal and antiseptic properties.

Fig. Tea tree oil.

Coconut Oil- The coconut oil has a soothing property. It moisturizes and nourishes the scalp. It also shows antifungal activity.

Apple Cider Vinegar- It is diluted with water and apply on the scalp with cotton and wash after 15-20 min. Due to its acidic nature it inhibits the fungus growth.

Fig. Apple cider vinegar

Neem Leaves- It is the traditional antifungal used since ancient times. The paste of neem leaves is to be applied on the infection and rinse off after drying.

Fig. Neem oil.

Amla oil- Amla oil is used as post treatment remedies. When the new hairs start to grow after treating infection. It helps to faster hair growth by providing nutrition to hair.

Fig. Amla oil.

Garlic extract, onion extract, rosemary oil, fenugreek seeds, etc. can often use as nutrition to hair.

4) Nutritional support - Besides of all medication, the dietary support needs to heal disease by our body mechanism. To heal infection, the main mechanism of body is to remove toxins from the body. The toxins provide nutritional support to the fungus for growth.

The diet we can follow to reduce toxins from body are as follows

A diet should contain - Vitamin C, Zinc, Probiotics, antifungal food like garlic, ginger, turmeric, etc.

Advanced treatment

1) PRP

PRP is a Platelet Rich Plasma therapy. PRP is one of the best therapies for hair regrowth after infection. It is used especially in cases of androgenetic alopecia i.e. baldness. Especially PRP is the platelets derived from own hair then concentrated to make a solution. Own Platelets is used as it contains growth factors which help to regeneration of tissue and healing as well as regeneration of hair follicles. The procedure involves-10-20 ml blood is taken from your body and then it centrifuged to separate the RBC and platelets rich in plasma. Then collected PRP is injected into the bald area of scalp. It increases the growth phase of hair cycle.

- The advantage of PRP includes- Minimum risk of allergic reaction because of using own blood. It repairs hair thinning. The clinical study states that more than 60% patients have shown positive response to the PRP
- There are some Disadvantages of PRP like- Redness of scalp, sometimes shows negative result as per the age and duration of hair loss, swelling of scalp, it is expensive, not useful for complete baldness.

Fig. Platelet Rich Plasma.

2) MICRONEEDLING

The micro needling is used for regrowth of hair after infection is treated completely. Micro needling is the process which includes a very fine needles to make tiny injuries on the scalp. It is the dermatological procedure for regrowth of hair. The tiny injuries help to increase production of collagen and growth factors into the hair. Micro needling includes- Increasing of blood flow into scalp, increase growth factors into scalp, and increase absorption of topically applied product. The main process involves that – Derma pen is used in treatment and it is 0.5-1.5mm in size. After injuries into the scalp, the topical antifungal is applied on the scalp like Minoxidil, hair growth serum, etc. To reduce infection micro needling is used in combination with Minoxidil for better treatment.

Advantages of micro needling include- Safe, affordable, can be done at home. Disadvantages of micro needling includes- Discomfort, Time taking results, contraindication for pregnant women.

Fig. Micro needling.

3) LEECH TREATMENT

Leech treatment is used especially for removing impure blood from body. Leech treatment is also known as Hirudotherapy, which basically comes under Ayurveda. The leech is applied on the bald area of hairs which is infected. Leech treatment involves the saliva of leech which is anti-inflammatory, anti-coagulant, Vasodilator and anti-microbial. The leech absorbs all the impure blood from the scalp and ultimately leads to decrease in infection. The impure blood gets removed and pure blood flow increases which can cause reducing fungal infection. After leech treatment the treatment like PRP, micro needling, derma-roller can be used. The process involves- First clean the infected area by maintaining proper hygiene and then apply leech on the area under physician consultation. This treatment should not be done when other treatments are going on.

Fig. Leech Treatment.

4) HORSETAIL EXTRACT

Horsetail extract is derived from a plant known as *Equisetum arvense*. It is the natural way for regrowth of hair. It increases hair growth on bald patches after the scalp infection. Horsetail

extract is rich in silica which help to improve scalp health post the infection. Horsetail extract includes anti-inflammatory and anti-oxidant property which reduce inflammation caused due to tinea capitis. Horsetail extract enhances circulation which leads to regrowth of hair. It also contains minerals like selenium, potassium which is helpful for regrowth of hair. It is used topically, apply the oil directly on the infected scalp combined with other hair growth factors. It has oral supplements, but it should take by consulting doctor. It should use 2 times per week. Advantage of Horsetail extract- Increases blood circulation in scalp, antioxidant, protect hair follicles, strengthen the hair, repairs hair.

Disadvantages of horsetail extract- Overuse can cause side effects, Contraindications in pregnancy, kidney disease.

Fig. Horsetail Extract Oil.

CONCLUSION

Tinea capitis is the major problem related to hairs among the children. The causes of hair infection are by infected animal or person, and by the organisms called as *Microsporum* and *Trichophyton* species. The two forms of infection are inflammatory and non-inflammatory. Its clinical features are from mild painful hair loss patches to very painful and scarring lesions. The treatment includes Oral antifungal, topical antifungal, herbal treatment, etc. The modern therapies include leech treatment, PRP, etc. Nutritional supplements can also use to make immune system strong. The main objective of treatment is to kill the fungus and avoid transmission. The treatment should be safe, irreversible and non-toxic. To prevent the fungal infection, it is important to maintain hygiene, to avoid direct contact with infected person, take care of hair and scalp etc. There are researches are going on for the advance therapy of the disease.

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